

THE ROLE OF EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN MARKETING

Dhumale Pramod Suryakant

*Asst. Professor, Dept. of English,
RNC Arts, JDB Commerce & NSC Science
College, Nashik Road: 422101*

Beg Waseem Ahamad

*Asst. Professor, Dept. of Chemistry,
RNC Arts, JDB Commerce & NSC Science
College, Nashik Road: 422101*

- **Abstract :**

Effective Communication is one of the fundamental necessities of marketing policy. It is significant in any commerce environment and in numerous situations such as meetings or negotiations. Several professions, however, need more proficiency in communication skills; public relation is certainly one such profession. Professional marketing also gets benefit of superior communication skills. Hence the purpose of this paper is to identify and discuss the significance of effective communication skills in Marketing, specifically to those who want to use it for the business purpose as one of the tools to expand and develop their business.

- **Keywords :** Communication, Verbal Communication, Non-verbal Communication, Written Communication, Body Language, Tone, Public Speaking

- **Introduction :**

Developing communication skills can assist many aspects of one's life, from professional career, to social gathering or to one's family life. In today's hectic environment, one closely depends upon sharing information, resulting in greater emphasis being placed on having good communication skills.

Good verbal and non-verbal communication skills are essential in order to deliver and comprehend information fast and properly. Being able to communicate effectively is a crucial life skill and should not be ignored. It is important in presenting a product or examine to potential customers and convincing them to buy that service or product. Effective communication skills in the form of personal interface, group communications, written and visual messages are essential traits of the successful marketer. Communication can be defined as the method of understanding and sharing meaning. To communicate well first one needs to understand well. This can be achieved by Verbal (voice, pronunciation, tone), visual (e.g. images, graphs, maps, info graphics), Non-verbal (e.g. body language, eye contact, gestures, postures, facial expressions) and written communication (e.g. books, websites, emails).

- **Definition of Communication :**

1. *“Communication is transfer of information from one person to another, whether or not it elicits confidence. But the information transferred must be understandable to the receiver.”* – G. G. Brown

2. *“Communication is the intercourse by words, letters or messages.”* – Fred G. Meyer

The precise meaning of the word 'communicate' is 'to share' or 'to participate'. The dictionaries state that communication is the transmission of a message or information by speaking or writing. Another dictionary

states that communication is giving or exchanging information, signals, messages by talk or gestures or writing. Yet another definition says that communication is social interaction.

Communication is giving, receiving or exchanging thoughts, information, signals or messages through proper media, enabling individuals or groups to persuade, to request information, to provide information or to convey emotions. This broad definition includes body language, speaking skills and writing skills. It outlines the objectives of communication. It emphasizes listening as an essential aspect of communication.

- **Significant Aspects of Effective Communication Skills in Marketing:**

1. ***Speak Clearly and Concisely:***

Speaking clearly can sometimes be a dilemma since not everyone actually takes the time to improve in diction or word usage. For the best results, try to practice speaking in front of a mirror or recording yourself for playback. The last requirement is respect. Never disrespect someone that you just met. First impressions never truly go away, so make an attempt to present yourself as a confident and respectful business associate. If all you have to utter “Blah,” don’t say “Blah, Blah.”

2. ***Recognize Problems in Communication:***

For starters, the most common barriers in effective communication are language, or word usage. One cannot always presume that what sounds benevolent to you would strike others the same way. People can easily misunderstand or even distort a statement’s original meaning.

It is wise to stay away from saying anything questionable that might puzzle a listener, or inadvertently provoke an unconstructive response. Humour and mockery can also be difficult to get across. Humour should be reasonably obvious and nothing too droll, or else one could easily take offense to a flippant statement.

3. ***Learn How to Use Tone and Body Language:***

Together In trying to advance your own communication beware of a defensive posture or negative voice inflection. Once a person goes on the defensive, the conversation tends to twisting into oblivion. Make sure that you apply a friendly and welcoming posture, with open arms and a smile. If you sense yourself taking on protective gestures or even resorting to a defensive tone (perhaps provoked by the other person) then eliminate those telling signs. Don’t let feeling overpower good judgment. In fact, the misinterpretation of body language and tone of voice is one of the most common harms in the breakdown of communication. Even if you are saying something pleasing, if you show physical signs to the dissimilar, your message and your truthfulness will come under suspicion. So should be cautious while using it in any language and in any situation.

4. ***Never Assume Anything:***

Assumptions are another general trouble, whether they are self-fulfilled assumptions or just assuming that others see things in the exact same way that you perform. Never assume the truth of the matter is that most people do not observe things they way that you do, nor do they have the same approach as you do. The

less you assume would always be better. This falls under the category of making sure that your communication is always comprehensible.

5. *Recognize Communication Issues Caused by Technology:*

With the advent of new technologies also come novel technology related hurdles in communication. Sometimes messages can be misunderstood because of phone static. Furthermore, when communicating it by phone is common for people to use selective hearing (hearing what they want to hear), which can add to the trouble. New technology based communication problems might result from misplaced phone messages or unclear email messages. This form of impersonal communication frequently doesn't permit for non-verbal clues, although virtual conferencing is an ever-increasing trend. Other communication problems may result from keeping prejudices and stereotyping groups of individuals based on their race, gender, ethnic group, age or religion. Hence nothing is universally true of any kind of person; every man or woman should be offered the opportunity to prove him or herself based on well-organized work.

6. *Learn How to Talk:*

If you are trying to find someone to open up then attempt using open ended questions rather than yes or no interrogations. When reviewing your own tactful manner examine the way you approach people. Do you frighten them with close-ended questions or do you ask them in a positive manner how the both of you can make necessary changes to get a project, for example, moving more efficiently? The more efficient you can be with your communication the more successful you will be in person and in profession. Communication can be extremely powerful in helping you or it can harm you.

7. *Public Speaking:*

1. Public speaking skill is must since public relations and marketing professionals habitually find themselves in front of customers, journalists, community representatives or other groups. Effective public speaking skills are a combination of audience study, speech writing and speech delivery. Marketing and public relations professionals recognize and act in response to the needs of their customers. Compelling speeches begin with an attention getting statement and contain a clear thesis, preview of main points, main points, and summary. Delivery skills include eye contact, a verity of pitch and smooth vocal rate, and very few vocal types of filler, such as "ah" or "like."

8. *Team Communications:*

Marketers work together daily with a large variety of personality kinds, such as business managers, artists, computer scientists, magazine and newspaper journalists, clients and company executives. All communicate differently and speak the language particular to their roles. Successful marketers are experts at listening and understanding the requirements and communications of each type of personality and job situation. They delight all they interact with as equals and negotiate effectively with each stakeholder to ensure marketing objectives are met. Marketers are open to new approaches and aim to apply expert suggestions when possible.

9. Speak in Specifics:

Good communicators aren't persuasive because they converse in dramatic, sweeping rhetoric. They're able to convince people because they can peak to specific examples or anecdotes that support the point they're trying to make and in the case of salesmen, because they can exhibit precisely how a merchandise or feature will help out their buyers.

10. Master the Gradation of Voice Tone:

Like body language, voice tone, voice pitch, volume, speed, and even one's word selection affects how the words one actually saying are interpreted. And if you're in sales, the only thing you have to make a sense is your voice tone.

Listen to how your prospect speaks, and then mirror their speaking patterns when it makes sense. While you almost certainly shouldn't imitate every slang word or language they use, slow down if other speak slowly or speed things up if they talk rapidly. One should always match his or her level of formality and familiarity to prospect well.

• Suggestions:

1. Learn the basics of non-verbal communication
2. Avoid depending on visual aids
3. Ask for honest feedback
4. Engage the audience in discussion
5. Start and end with key points
6. Record important presentations for posterity
7. Master the art of timing
8. Get to know your audience
9. Add novelty to improve audience retention

• Conclusion:

The survey has identified that the role played by communication during change in the business organizations is crucial for successful change in management. The employees are the key sources to bring about change in any organizations. To encourage employees for desired change, organizations should concentrate on the apprehensions and issues related with them. Job uncertainty should be decreased and a sense of community should be created so that employees may experience their responsibilities. The need for transform and its advantages will stimulate the employees to take part in modification, planning and executing it properly.

• References:

- Gilley, A., Gilley, J. W., & Mc Milan, H. S. (2009). Organizational Change: Motivation, Communication, and Leadership Effectiveness. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*
- Tucker, M. L., Meyer, G. D., & Waterman, J. W. (1996). Organizational Communication: Development of internal strategic competitive advantage. *The Journal of Business Communication*

- Postmas, T., Tanis, M., & de Wit, B. (2001). Communication & commitment in organizations: A social identity approach. *Group Processes and Intergroup Relations*
- Lewis, L. K. (2000). Communicating change: Four cases of quality programs. *E-Journal of Business Communication*
- Martin, C.I., (1990). Enhancing the Effectiveness of student & oral presentations. *Marketing Education Review*
- **Websites –**
 1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Communication>
 2. <https://www.communicationtheory.org/definitions-of-communication>